

Recovering **metals** and **mineral fraction**
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable 2.1

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Abbreviations and acronyms

- BF** – Blast Furnace
- BOF** – Basic Oxygen Furnace
- BOFD** – Basic Oxygen Furnace Dust
- EAF** – Electric Arc Furnace
- EAFD** - Electric Arc Furnace Dust
- H** – Hisarna Process
- LF** – Ladle Furnace
- SEM-EDS** – Scanning Electron Microscopy – Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy
- TRL** – Technology Readiness Level
- XRD** – X-Ray Diffraction
- XRF** – X-Ray Fluorescence

Abstract

The present report details the requirements of the Plasma reactor process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters.

Historical data of steelmaking residues with high metallic or oxidic fractions are provided by several industrial partners (DALMINE, VAS, TATA, TKSE, and CELSA) and then collected in a common database developed by RINA-CSM; such data comprise annual production rates and physical/chemical characterization.

RINA-CSM and TENOVA will perform heat and material balances for Plasma Reactor by using a flowchart software model. The outputs of the model are:

- ✓ Estimation of the specific number of products and by-products,
- ✓ Definition of resulting temperatures of material streams (e. g. process gas/exhaust gas)
- ✓ Determination of electric energy consumption
- ✓ Definition of reducing agent quantities
- ✓ Definition of suitable residue processing scenarios with the range of suitable input material (mix) qualities and expected outputs (hot metal, slag, waste gas).

1 Introduction

The objective of the ReMFra project is to demonstrate and qualify a complete system for the recovery and the valorization of the metal and mineral fractions contained in steel making processing residues, to improve the metal recovery yield, to reach the full circularity and to reduce the environmental impacts of the steel sector all over Europe. This will be achieved thanks to the commercialization of the ReMFra plants that will start soon after the project conclusion.

The two technologies (Plasma reactor and RecoDust process) considered will be combined to maximize the efficiency of metal and mineral recovery, aiming to achieve a TRL > 8, i.e., system completed and qualified. To do that, it is essential to assess the specifics required for the feed to be used and to link it to the technology to consider; therefore, the database created in Task 2.1, composed of the historical data provided from the industrial partners involved (DALMINE, VAS, TATA, TKSE, and CELSA) and the thermodynamic modelling carried out by RINA-CSM, is essential to detect the optimal recipe of materials.

The database will be used to detail the requirements of the Plasma reactor process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters.

2 Collection and classification of the residues

The steel producers being partners of the ReMFra project shared sensitive information about their production when providing data about the residues selected. Firstly, a primary classification regarded the type of steel production cycle:

- Electric Cycle: Dalmine and Celsa
- Integral Cycle: Tata, VAS, and TKSE

Following, the residues were grouped into the three main categories reported below:

- Slags
- Scales and Sludges
- Dusts

The whole classification might be observed in Figure 1, differentiating the production types and reporting the specific residues provided by the partners.

In Table 1, are listed all the materials considered for the project.

Figure 1: Overview of the classification set up for the residues considered in ReMFra

Table 1: Overview of the materials considered for the ReMFra project

Production Line	Main Group	Residue
Electric Cycle	Slags	EAF Slag
		LF Slag
		LF Slag (Granulated)
		EAF Slag
		LF Slag
	Scales and Sludges	Scale
		Rolling Mill Sludge
		Wet Pickling Sludge
		Dried Pickling Sludge
		Mill scale I
		Mill scale II
		Mill scale III
	Dusts	EAFD
		EAFD

Integral Cycle	Slags	H Slag
		LD Slag
	Scales and Sludges	BF Sludge (Coarse)
		BF Sludge Filter Press
		Oily Mill Scale Sludge
		BOF Sludge
		Rolling Mill Sludge
	Dusts	BFD
		BOF Dust (Fine)
		BOF Dust (Coarse)
		H Dust (A)
		H Dust (B)
		BOFD (Coarse)
		BOFD (Fine)

2.1 Grain Size distribution

The grain size distribution analysis is essential for a correct and comprehensive evaluation of the materials to be considered for the ReMFra technologies since finer materials would be more suitable to the RecoDust process whereas the coarser ones would better fit the plasma reactor.

Moreover, in ReMFra reactor briquettes will be charged to obtain a higher efficiency of reduction process. In the briquette production the mixture of fine and coarse materials permits

higher briquette densities to be achieved, allowing, during charging, to reach the interface metal bath/slag where the reaction starts.

In line with the preliminary requirements just discussed above, the materials provided were showing diversified grain size distributions; specifically, all the scales and sludges (apart from the BF Sludge Filter Press from the integral cycle representative) and the dusts were showing sizes below 1.0 mm, independently from the cycle considered. Please note that the detailed grain size distribution has been provided by all the partners for all the materials here discussed, and it is kept confidential within the ReMFRa consortium.

2.2 Chemistry – Oxide composition

The chemistry of the materials to be considered for the feed of ReMFRa reactor is crucial to the recovery of resources whilst ensuring an acceptable service life for the units, i.e., the consumption of the refractories must also be considered. Upon smelting, independently from the recipe used in the feed, three streams would arise: a metal phase ideally composed of liquid iron, a slag phase with an oxide composition resembling the feed, and a dust phase with an enriched fraction of ZnO. Said that, the optimal recipe (proportioning of the different materials reported in this document) to be used would allow for a high recovery of Fe and Zn, and that would depend on both the initial Fe and Zn contents within the feed, the reducing agent used, and the reducing condition inside the reactor. Given that this deliverable aims to select a range of options suitable for the Plasma reactor, and to assess the related operative conditions for two case studies (Dalmine and a representative of the integral cycle), only their punctual analyses are reported here. Regarding the chemical composition of the other materials provided by TATA, Celsa, and VAS, they have been provided and a detailed database has been shared within the consortium, but it is not here reported.

2.2.1 Electric Cycle – Dalmine

As reported in Figure 2 (and as expected), the EAF and LF slags provided by Dalmine were showing different chemical compositions, including the speciation of iron. FeO was a major component in the EAF Slag from Dalmine (37.0 wt.%), whereas lower contents were detected in the LF Slag (11.1 % Fe₂O₃). Both the slags were showing low contents (< 5.0 %) of other

metals, such as Cr, Mn, Ni, and Cu; the Zn contents were too low for these streams (< 0.5 wt.%).

Figure 2: Oxide (wt. %) composition of the LF and EAF slags

In terms of oxides, the LF Slag showed higher CaO contents (47.2 wt.%) than the EAF Slag (23.5 wt.%).

Regarding the sludges and scales, a higher variability in terms of Fe speciation was observed with respect to the slags just discussed (Figure 2). While both wet and dry pickling sludges are relatively poor in Fe (5.0 % and 13.6 % FeO, respectively), both the scale and rolling mill sludge have very high contents of iron. Specifically, the scale was composed of 64.6 % Fe₂O₃ and 28.7 % Fe₃O₄, and the rolling mill sludge of 45.3 % Fe₂O₃ and 32.1 % Fe₃O₄ (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Oxide (wt. %) composition of the Scale, Rolling Mill Sludge, Wet Pickling Sludge, and Dry Pickling Sludge

The rolling mill sludge is the only material within this list with a high carbon content (14.3 %); the Al₂O₃ content was low for all these materials, while low CaO and SiO₂ contents could be detected for the scale and the rolling mill sludge. Finally, a 62 wt.% water content was detected in the wet pickling sludge.

Dalmine also provided the dusts from EAF. As reported in Figure 4, FeO is the main constituent (41.7 wt.%), whereas a low ZnO content (5.0 wt.%) was detected.

Figure 4: Oxide (wt. %) composition of the EAFD

2.2.2 Integral Cycle

The chemical compositions of the scales and sludges arising from the integral cycle representative, are discussed in this sub-section and reported in Figure 5 below. The chemical analysis of the BF Sludge (Coarse), the BF Sludge Filter Press, and the Oily Mill Scale Sludge from an integral cycle representative showed quite different Fe_{Tot} (31.5 wt.%, 20.3 wt.%, and 69.8 wt.%, respectively) and C (37.9 %, 34.4 %, and 6.2 %, respectively) contents. Upon smelting, the very low CaO (0.5 – 6.0 wt.%) and MgO (< 2.0 wt.%) contents, with the BF sludge filter press showing a slightly higher fraction of MgO, would lead to an acidic (0.5 – 0.6) final slag phase.

Figure 5: Oxide (wt. %) composition of the BF Sludge (Coarse), BF Sludge Filter Press, and Oily Mill Scale Sludge

Regarding the dusts from the integral cycle representative, the iron content was significantly different when considering the BFD (around 25 wt.%) and the BOFD (> 60 wt.%); slight differences were observed between the fine and coarse BOFDs, mainly differing for the CaO content (with the latter being about three times higher than the former). In terms of carbon, the BFD was about 50 wt.%, much higher than both the BOFD (~2 wt.%), while the fine BOFD showed a relatively high ZnO content (2.6 wt. %), when compared to the coarse BOFD (0.9 wt.%) and the BFD (0.2 wt.%).

Figure 6: Oxide (wt. %) composition of the BFD, BOFD (Fine), and BOFD (Coarse)

3 Plasma Reactor

Plasma Reactor is based on plasma technology (electrical arc generated by graphite electrodes) working in reducing atmosphere. This pyrometallurgical process has been selected since it can treat a large variety of waste streams. In the ReMFra project the Plasma Reactor is applied for the treatment of residues containing high percentage of iron: scale from rolling mill, sludge from cooling water circuits, EAF/BOF dusts and slags.

The basic phenomenon occurring during the process are the following:

- 1) The heating of the briquettes/pellets (up to process temperature – 1600 °C);
- 2) The reduction of Fe_xO_y to Fe;
- 3) Melting of inert, FeO and Fe;
- 4) Dissolution of FeO into the slag.

To define the operating condition ranges, mass and energy balance has been performed by thermodynamic calculation. This permits also to evaluate the pre-defined quality of metal and slag, and to calculate the amount of reducing agent and the energy demand of the process (Figure 7).

Moreover, to have the highest efficiency in the reduction reaction, the materials will be charged in the reactor after briquetting treatment. The briquettes produced with a density higher than the slag, charged from the top of the reactor pass through the slag layer till the metal/slag interface, where the reaction can start.

Moreover, alternative agglomeration technologies will be evaluated by TKSE such as pelletizing technology.

The model gives the first indication about a possible recipe for the briquettes and pellets.

3.1 Mass and energy balance

In the definition of the calculation, some assumptions have been made. For the mass balance (Figure 7):

- ✓ The distribution of the different chemical species between metal bath, slag and dust has been defined on the basis of literature data and previous experimental activities, and industrial tests,
- ✓ The metal bath has the 3% of carbon content
- ✓ The coal used for reduction has 10 % of ash content

For the energy balance:

- ✓ It has been assumed that the temperature of melting and reduction is 1600°C. For this reason, the thermodynamic parameters have been calculated at 1600°C
- ✓ In the reduction reaction only CO is generated
- ✓ The process gas has the same temperature of the process, 1600°C.

In the choice of the possible charging material mix, it is important to fix some points:

- ✓ The ratio of produced amounts of ferro alloy/slag, has to be not less than 1.5.
- ✓ The composition of the produced slag has to have an IB2 (IB2-CaO/SiO₂), between 1,2-1,8.

Figure 7: Scheme reporting the input and output regarding the plasma reactor

An important parameter to be considered is the behavior of the slag during the process with particular regard to the foaming aspect. Slag foaming is a common practice in EAF process. The main advantages of the foaming slag practice in EAF are:

- ✓ Heat transfer: submerging the arc in the slag can enhance the heat transfer between the arc and the melt.
- ✓ Refractory protection: furnace wall and roof are shielded from arc radiation after melting down.
- ✓ Increase of process stability

The foaming can be difficult to control properly since the evolution of the chemical and physical conditions in the slag/steel system that affect foam height is generally unknown.

Foam is generated by the gas (CO) passing through the liquid slag; the foam height depends on slag properties and velocity of the gas.

In the design of the reactor this phenomenon has to be considered. Moreover, the amount of slag inside the furnace must be sufficient to ensure target productivity. During the process the slag mass inside the EAF changes because of materials feeding, reduction of FeO and slag tapping. Feeding and tapping strategy must be designed to maintain the optimum range of slag amount and FeO concentration.

3.2 Briquettes definition

The first composition of the briquettes will be defined starting from the annual tons of residues to be treated. To produce briquettes with optimal characteristics, it will be required to balance several aspects related to the recipe used, such as: low energy input, proportionate reducing

conditions, metal-to-slag phases ratio around two, and basicity of the slag bath to fall between 1.6 and 1.7. Apart from all the parameters just mentioned, the model also allowed for the assessment of the carbon needed to reduce the input species, aiming to a metal bath with 3 wt.% of carbon.

The following sections report the calculations done for the operation of the Plasma Reactor with the residues provided by Dalmine; for completion, representative compositions of the integrated steel cycle were also considered, and preliminary calculations were also carried out.

3.2.1 Dalmine

Out of the materials provided by Dalmine, LF slag, Scale, Rolling Mill Sludge (Dalmine), EAFD, and Dry Pickling Sludge were considered for the feeding of the plasma reactor; upon proportioning of those components, three potential recipes were selected (Table 2), and they are discussed below. For the recipes, the full consumption of both the scale and EAFD was taken as a starting point, whereas the dry pickling sludge (arising from the Costa Volpino plant) was solely considered for recipe # 2 (since both the annual generation and the low-to-medium risk linked to its disposal do not strictly require its processing in these terms). The wet pickling sludge was not considered here, since the briquetting will require a certain grade of moisture to be achieved, and therefore further considerations will be applied when practically making the briquettes. Recipe # 1 (reference scenario) was designed to use the total amount annually produced of the Scale, Rolling Mill Sludge, and EAFD, as declared by Dalmine (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**); the LFS was gradually increased to balance the composition of the final slag, leading to the target binary (CaO and SiO₂) basicity of 1.6, whilst ensuring a sufficient metal-to-slag ratio. Recipe # 2 was designed to include the dry pickling sludge into the briquetting design, with LFS used to balance the system again. Recipe # 3 can be divided into two different types of briquettes, a proper one made of the same proportions used in recipe # 1 but at a lower scale content (labelled as # 3 Pt.1); the remaining amount of scale not used for the first type of briquettes will be blended with plastic (available and to be used at Dalmine) to make a separate agglomerate (labelled as # 3 Pt.2) to be fed into the Plasma reactor together with # 3 Pt.1. For the briquette type # 3 Pt.2, the plastic considered has an average density of 0.4 t/m³, and an overall 60 wt.% C content. To avoid problems during

the feed into the Plasma reactor, i.e., solids with too low density would float on the slag bath, lowering the surface contact and therefore overall efficiency, calculations were done to ensure an overall density of 2 t/m³ for the briquette # 3 Pt.2. Considering the remaining amount of scale to be processed (7,200 t/y, complementary with the 16,800 t/y used for # 3 Pt.1) and the average density (2.5 t/m³), the briquette # 3 Pt.2 should be made of 76 wt.% Scale and 24 wt.% plastic. The individual proportions considered for # 3 Pt.1 and # 3 Pt.2 are reported in Table 2 below together with the overall recipe # 3.

Table 2: Weight fractions of LF slag, Scale, Rolling Mill Sludge (Dalmine), EAFD, Dry Pickling Sludge, and Wet Pickling Sludge considered to produce the briquettes type 1 - 3

Recipe No.	LF Slag [%]	Scale [%]	Rolling mill sludge [%]	EAFD [%]	Dry Pickling Sludge [%]	Plastic [%]
# 1	19	68	10	3	0	0
# 2	21	65	9	3	2	0
# 3 Pt.1	20	63	13	4	0	0
# 3 Pt.2	0	76	0	0	0	24
# 3	18	63	10	3	0	6

Figure 8 shows the recycling rate linked to the recipes proposed, i.e., the tons per year which could be ideally processed (and therefore recycled) with respect to the amounts declared; as already mentioned, all the recipes were considering a full use of EAFD and Scale, with # 3 dividing the total amount of scale into the first (# 3 Pt.1) and second (# 3 Pt.2) type of briquettes.

Figure 8: Comparison between the annual production declared by Dalmine and the portion which would be processed through the Plasma reactor, considering the compositions # 1, # 2, and # 3

As reported in Figure 9A, the different proportioning used for the three recipes led to slightly varying amounts of metal and slag phases; specifically, the recipe # 2 showed a higher (1.9) metal-to-slag ratio, with 546 kg_{Metal} and 290 kg_{Slag}, than Recipe # 1 (1.7) and Recipe # 3 (1.6) per ton of material processed. Even the amounts of dusts generated were similar, ranging between 10 and 12 kg per t of input; however, given the different proportioning used for the considering that the ZnO within the dusts is assessed at around 19 wt.%, about 1.5 kg of metallic Zn can be ideally recovered per ton of input. With respect to the energy required to smelt the feeds considered (Figure 9B), recipes # 1 and # 3 showed a lower energy input (1833 and 1826 kWh/t_{Feed}, respectively) with respect to # 2 (1866 kWh/t_{Feed}). Finally, the model allowed to predict the approximate composition of the slags arising from the Plasma reactor upon smelting of the input streams. As reported in Figure 9B, all the slags generating from the recipes # 1, # 2, and # 3 were highly similar; in fact, they were all leading to the targeted basicity (binary, i.e., CaO/SiO₂) values of 1.6.

Figure 9: Metal, slag, dust phases (kg/t_{Feed}), and energy input calculated for the three recipes to be considered for Dalmine (A), and composition of the resulting slag phases (B)

Table 3 below reports some key parameters necessary to the technical engineering of the Plasma reactor and of the process, including the volume of the reactor (depending on the height achieved by the metal bath and the foam of the slag), the volume and heat of the off-gas before and after Zn recovery (off-gas and post-combustion, respectively), the energy demand for the process, the coal to be added for oxides reduction. Again, the weighted sum of the types of briquettes for recipe # 3 was considered.

Table 3: Calculated parameters related to the use of the recipes 1 – 3 with the materials from Dalmine, necessary for the engineering of the plasma reactor

Recipe No.	1	2	3
Charge rate (t/h)	7.40	7.80	7.90
Charge (t/heat)	22.20	23.40	23.80
Coal (kg/t _{Feed})	161.00	154.00	139.00
Energy (kWh/t _{Feed})	1868.00	1843.90	1795.00
Off-gas flow (Nm ³ /t)	227.00	218.50	252.10
Off-gas heat (kWh/t)	163.00	169.30	193.70
Height metal (m)	0.35	0.36	0.35
Max height foam (m)	1.62	1.71	1.84

For Dalmine, some first calculation for reactor volume was made starting from the ladle diameter. This is to control the formation of foam during the reduction reaction.

The foaming can be difficult to control properly since the evolution of the chemical and physical conditions in the slag/steel system that affect foam height is generally unknown.

Foam is generated by the gas (CO) passing through the liquid slag; the foam height depends on slag properties and velocity of the gas. Following a classical formulation to calculate slag height.

$$H_{foam} = \Sigma \cdot velocity_{gas}$$

Where Σ is a foaming index, depending on slag characteristics: viscosity (μ), density (ρ) and surface tension (σ)

$$\Sigma = k \cdot \frac{\mu}{(\rho \cdot \sigma)^{1/2}}$$

Where: k is a coefficient specific for slag type. For the slag composition calculated with this first briquette composition k ~ 214¹.

Knowing the reactor diameter, it is possible to calculate the H of the foaming slag, as follows:

$$H_{foam} = \Sigma \cdot velocity_{gas}$$

$$velocity_{gas} = \frac{FlowRate}{Area}$$

Based on the present recipes of briquettes the waste gas flow rate and temperature after complete post-combustion, to reach an oxygen excess about 12% in vol., will be:

		LOAD CASE #1	LOAD CASE #2	LOAD CASE #3
Flow rate	Nm ³ /h	8619	8716	12580
Temperature inlet HRSG (dedusting system)	°C	1469	1467	1443
Oxygen excess	%	12,0	12,0	12,0

By means of a solution of heat recovery for steam generation (HRSG) it is possible to partial recover the waste heat available in the off-gas. The aim of the HRSG system is to produce saturated steam converting the thermal power contained in the waste gas produced during the ReMFra process and transfer it to the steam plant network for further use. The HRSG is composed of a steam generation section and a distribution section; the former comprises all the technologies involved in steam generation, i.e., feed water station, waste gas duct with recirculation system and/or the waste heat boiler, the steam accumulator, and the control valves for pressure control and flow distribution.

¹ ISIJ International, Vol. 41 (2001), No. 4, pp. 317–324

In the steam generation section, all the cooled parts of the HRSG system in direct contact with the waste gas are equipped by an evaporative cooling system. In the ECS circuits the circulating water, at boiling temperature, is forced to circulate into the water circuits of the waste gas duct by means of forced circulation through proper sized recirculation pumps. The results presented in this paragraph consider a heat exchange surface for the ECS section about 134m².

In the Waste Heat Boiler (WHB), the circulating water (T~100°C) is driven from a steam drum into a series of tubes and pipes, where the energy is absorbed. The WHB in natural circulation will consist of four tube banks (surface of 48m²) one and two economizers (surface of 32m²).

Figure 10: General scheme of HRSG

The steam - water mixture returning to the steam drum is separated into saturated steam, available for the steam network, and water at the boiling point, that will be naturally fed back into the cooled sections.

The steam produced by the forced and/or naturally circulated circuits is transferred to distribution section. The main technology in this HRSG section is the steam accumulator which plays two roles, because the EAF is batch process, to ensure the steam feeding to the network even during the EAF power-off. The amount of steam delivered to the steam network has to be replaced by feed water coming from a feed water station. It consists of a feed water tank equipped with thermal deaerator and a feed water pump station properly sized.

Considering the following pressure chain for the presented equipment:

HRSG PRESSURE CHAIN	Operating Pressure [bar(g)]	Operating Temperature [°C]
TOP 1 - Steam delivery to network	16,0	204,3
Operating pressure at steam drum min.	19,0	209,8
Operating pressure at steam drum max.	26,0	226,1
Set point blow-off valve	26,0	228,1
Pressure switch (PZH)	27,0	230,1
Safety valve open pressure (PS)	28,0	233,9
Diff. pressure feed water pump	34,8	104,8

The heat recovered by this system is represented in the following table:

		LOAD CASE #1	LOAD CASE #2	LOAD CASE #3
Thermal power available	MW	6576	6625	8923
Thermal power recovered	MW	5972	6012	7911
Temperature outlet HRSG OUT	°C	184	184	211
Steam production	ton/h	8,2	8,2	10,6
Steam pressure at TOP	bar(g)	16	16	16
Temperature pressure at TOP	°C	204,3	204,3	204,3

3.2.2 Integral cycle representative

The BFD, BF Sludge (Coarse), BF Sludge Filter press, BOFD (Fine), BOFD (Coarse), and the oily mill scale sludge, representative of a conventional integral steel cycle, were considered for the briquetting and following feed into the plasma reactor. As for the materials provided by Dalmine, the same calculations were done to define the key parameters related to a given recipe, i.e., the energy required to operate the plasma reactor, the composition and basicity of the slag, the metal-to-slag ratio, and the amount of dust. In this case the volume of the reactor was not calculated.

Preliminary calculations were carried out to define the three potential recipes outlined in Table 4 below; no carbon addition is required for the reduction given the high content within all these materials.

Table 4: Weight fractions (wt.%) of BFD, BF Sludge (Coarse), BF Sludge Filter Press, BOFD (Fine), and oily mill scale sludge, used to produce the briquettes type 1 - 3

Recipe No.	BFD	BF Sludge (Coarse)	BF Sludge Filter Press	BOFD (Fine)	BOFD (Coarse)	Oily mill scale sludge
1	30	2	7	40	18	3
2	18	3	10	60	4	5
3	19	1	3	50	23	4

Recipe # 1 was done by assuming the total consumption of the industrial streams from a representative of the integral cycle, and that was taken as a basis for # 2, which was characterized by a higher content of basic species, i.e., CaO-containing streams. Recipe # 3 was finally drafted by maximizing the amount of metal recoverable from the streams, whilst keeping the overall carbon content high to avoid external supply. As reported in Figure 10, Recipe # 1 is the only one allowing for the complete recycling of all the conventional streams from the integrated steel cycle.

Figure 10: Comparison between the annual production of the representative integral cycle and the portion which would be processed through the Plasma reactor, considering the compositions # 1, # 2, and # 3

Figure 11A and B show the amounts of metal and slag phases ideally recoverable from the processing of each recipe; the candidate # 3 would allow for a higher metal recovery than # 1 and # 2.

However, the composition # 2 was the one with the highest metal-to-slag ratio of 3.0, whereas # 1 and # 3 showed values of 2.4 and 2.5, respectively. Likely linked to the highest carbon content, the amount of dusts from recipe # 2 was higher (25.3 kg per ton of feed) than # 1 (20.8) and # 3 (22.8). Given that the dusts of the different recipes were showing similar values around 69 wt.%, in optimal conditions it would be possible to recover about 12.7, 16.7, and 14.2 kg_{Zn} per ton of # 1, # 2, and # 3, respectively.

Figure 11: Metal, slag, dust phases (kg/tFeed), and energy input calculated for the three recipes to be considered for the representative integral cycle (A), and composition of the resulting slag phases (B)

In terms of energy demand, the candidate # 3 appeared to be the best given the 1031.5 kWh/t_{Feed} calculated, lower than # 1 (1050.6 kWh/t_{Feed}) and # 2 (1039.4 kWh/t_{Feed}). Therefore, while Recipe # 2 would allow for the highest metal-to-slag ratio and the highest Zn content within the dusts, Recipe # 3 showed the lowest energy consumption. However, the chemistry of the slag resulting from the smelting of the streams (Figure 11A) would represent a problem to the overall efficiency of metal recovery from Recipe # 3, showing a basicity index (CaO/SiO₂) of 2.0. On the contrary, Recipes # 1 and # 2 were showing basicity indexes of 1.6 and 1.4, respectively.

To adjust this, the briquettes could be further engineered by adding SiO₂, to enhance the acidity of the slag and lower the basicity to a value of 1.6. Considering that about the 92 % of the Si fed into the plasma reactor would pass into slag phase, Table 5 below reports the adjusted Recipe # 3 upon addition of SiO₂.

Table 5: Adjusted weight fractions (wt.%) of BFD, BF Sludge (Coarse), BF Sludge Filter Press, BOFD (Fine), and oily mill scale sludge, upon addition of SiO₂

Recipe No.	BFD	BF Sludge (Coarse)	BF Sludge Filter Press	BOFD (Fine)	BOFD (Coarse)	Oily mill scale sludge	SiO ₂
3	16	1	3	43	19	4	14

3.3 Pellets definition

For residues such as Blast Furnace dust, alternative agglomeration technologies will be evaluated by TKSE (pelletizing technology). The pellets quality must meet the Plasma Reactor process requirements.

In principle the recipe defined for briquettes can be also used for first laboratory pellets production.

The first step of pellets production is the materials preparation. The raw materials will be used as received, mixed in the aimed proportions and added with the binder/additive and water.

The mix is pelletized on a disk, adding the minimum water needed to stabilize pelletizing conditions. The green pellets thus produced should have the following characteristics:

Table 6: Green pellets requirements

Compression strength [kg/pellets]		Drop number [N°]	Bulk density [kg/dm ³]	
Wet	Dry	Wet	Wet	Dry
> 2	> 4	>15	>1.3	>1.2

After drying and heating, the quality requirements are the following:

Table 7: Pellets requirements

Compression strength [kg/pellets]	Drop number [N°]	Tumbler test		Apparent density [kg/dm ³]
		TI [%]	TA [%]	
>20	>10	>50%	>5%	>2

4 Conclusions

The present report details the requirements of the Plasma reactor process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters.

The database provided by each partner allowed to propose potential candidates for the making of the briquettes and pellets to be used in the Plasma reactor; each recipe has been selected in accordance with crucial parameters arising from the calculations based on the thermodynamics of the systems.

As outlined above, three candidates for Dalmine and a representative of the integral steel cycle have been selected; for Dalmine, both the thermodynamic properties of the resulting streams and the technical parameters required for the design of the reactor (Tenova) were provided. Based on the conventional data from integral steel cycles, the recipes of the eventual briquettes were formulated as well. Regarding TKSE, the procedure for the preparation of the pellets has been defined.

Briquettes from Dalmine and pellets from TKSE will be characterized at RINA-CSM laboratories with melting tests to define the kinetic of reaction and the recovery metal yield.